

Self-Esteem among Counselling Students in High Education in Sultanate of Oman

Dr. Esam Al-lawati, Assistant professor of psychology, Head of Psychology Department, College of Arts & Humanities, A'Sharqiyah University - Oman
email: esam.allawati@asu.edu.om

Abstract

In current study, researcher tries to identify the self-esteem among Psychology students in A'Sharqiyah University (ASU) in Sultanate of Oman. This study was conducted to around (n=93) undergraduate Bachelor of Counselling students from College of Art and Humanities in ASU. The researcher used self-esteem scale among psychology students so that fits and suits the local environment in the Sultanate of Oman which is prepared by Rosenberg (1979) and it was modified by the researcher in order to suit the peculiarity of the local community. The research assume that there are several factors can effects the level of self-esteem with high education students; such as gender, age, grade and finally social status. Results of the current study showed that self-esteem and for both male and female students in high education in College of Art and Humanities in ASU in Oman affected by age factor. Where the results showed that the student at the university level increases his/her self-esteem as he/she progresses in age. This study found there is no significant differences in level of self-esteem between male and females, where both male and female students was characterized by clear rise in self-esteem. Also, this study found that level of self-esteem is adversely affected due to the transition from adolescences stage to adulthood stage. Where the student in adolescence is an estimate of itself is weaker than it is at the university level (American Psychological Association, 2002). The results of the current study found the academic year variable is not statistically significant. Finally, the results of current study have significant effects for parent, educationalists and students where the considerate on self-esteem might develop their understanding, knowledge and scientific prospect about everything that goes on around them and also they can understand themselves and the society around them.

Keywords: *Self-esteem, Criticism, Negative Feedback, Adolescence.*

Introduction

Self-esteem is an essential and important portion of an individual experience and particularity of human life (Crocker & Wolfe, 2001). An affirmative self-appraisal is a fundamental indicator of individual luxury and level of acclimation to the public situation of whole society, as well as an essential and important aspect in protecting against psycho-social risks in late childhood stage and also in adolescence stage (Forzi& Not, 2003).

There are so many researchers has been concerned about Self-Esteem in ninetieth and twentieth century such as; William James (1890), Rosenberg (1965; 1979), Branden (1969; 1994) and Mruk (1999). The concept of Self-Esteem considered as main concepts that give a key indicator for human's adaptation with environment and community. William James (1890) mentioned that self-esteem arises when person interact with others either in school or in work environment and other places. He viewed self-esteem as main proportion of the individual's successes. However, he believed that person become failure because of imbalance of his/her self-esteem.

Also, Rogers (1961) explained concept of self-esteem in terms of the disproportion that exists among the ideal self and the real self and he perceived to the social humanity as main source of information and understanding (ideal self) in opposition to which the individual evaluates his/her practical rendering and therefore his/her level of self-esteem is determined.

Vygotsky (1978) believed that children improving and develop while their interacting with society and many concepts and ideas rises. Also he believed that cultural world considered as incentives to them and this will experience as the criterion against which child actions are evaluated and his/her stage of self-esteem is determined.

Over the last century, many researchers have been conduct about self-esteem and how this concept influence human behavior and also and how it affects the high self-esteem as well as high academic performance at school and university students in general. Contrariwise, low self-esteem was linked with many individual and social concerns, such as school weakness, depression, social apprehension, hostility, drug addiction. (Cooper Smith 1967).

Furthermore, the results of the studies on self-esteem indicate that this concept (self-esteem) is formed in human life through the contradiction between the individual's goals and achievements and the amount of exciting support obtain by parents, teachers and educators. Self-esteem affects the individual's personal experiences, either negatively or positively. For example, when someone does something and succeeds in their tasks, he/she gets positive feedback about his/her performance and so it will support and grow

his/her self-esteem. However, when the contradiction is huge the individual will notice or perceive him as weakness to rises the level of particular goals, and then, leads to reduction self-esteem (Tam & Fatimah, 2009).

Self-Esteem

The meaning of Self-esteem is how we evaluate ourselves; it is how we recognize our value to the society and how valuable we think we are toward ourselves and others. Self-esteem has different affects with person life, it has affects how person create a positive relationships based on trust, either in work environment or with his/her friends or the relationships within family– almost every portion of person's live. Positive self-esteem gives person the power and pliability to take charge of ourselves and reduce our misconception without be scared of denial or disapproval.

While Malbi & Reasoner (2000) defined self-esteem as the overall estimation of us in either an optimistic or pessimistic way. It indicates the extent to which a person believes himself / herself to be adequate and valuable of living (Malbi & Reasoner, 2000).

Self-Esteem Risk Factors

Criticism: Exposure to continuous criticism leads to an individual's sense of irrelevance and unwanted.

Discrimination in treatment between children: lead to a sense of low value of the individual and insignificant.

Physical and mental abuse: leads to an individual's sense of worthlessness and is not desirable.

Naughty labels and titles: Sometimes parents call their children names that hurt their self-esteem, such as: stupid, lazy, bad boy, etc. These labels may have a few meanings, but they convey messages that suggest dishonesty and importance and must be replaced.

Negative Feedback: Respondents and even mentors need a good amount of feedback about their efforts to develop a virtue or behavior. They need to assess their behavior and to be recognized, which results in greater appreciation.

The Language: Language considered as most important factor which have a great impact on human, for instance, if parent used a negative language such as using contempt or mockery words, his/her self-esteem

will affected and then will reduction. Whereas recognizing virtues and using positive words such as respect and appreciation, this leads to more desirable behavior and increases self-esteem. (Ragda, 2007).

Self-Esteem & Lifespan Stages

Most researchers agree on the self-esteem is formed in humans from a young age, particularly since his/her birth and for this, the researcher will be exposed the concept of self-esteem at all stages of human age.

Childhood

Self-esteem is one of the important concepts in the education and refinement our children because children feel accepted and valued by their parents and other adults and who are important to them. The growth of a sense of self is very complicated. Most of the research findings indicate that self-esteem developed from within a person and all components of environment are interfere to shape this attribute of the personality traits (Katz, 1996). Being capable to administrate his or her life, feelings and resolution comes from the basis of an intense sensation of self. Being capable to administrate helps people cope with difficult situation when they encountering.

Many researchers believe that self-esteem development particularly with children, coming in various stages. The first stage of self-esteem in children is a sense of confidence in the people around him such as parents, siblings and friends. This stage is very important because it gives impression of self-respect and a sense of respect and appreciation of this. Subsequently, and through parents deal with their children and give them affection and social warmth, also through social and emotional response, children will gain self with themselves and with others, confidence and this will increase self-esteem.

Some researchers tend to children have relatively reasonable proportion of self-esteem and gradually this appreciation and respect start to reduce but this point of view this lacks credibility and it close to fiction. (Richard et al, 2002).

Through the knowledge growth of children they begin to assess their social comparisons and peripheral reactions reported outside their reaction in a balanced manner, through the knowledge and increase the gradient to acquire social skills. A good example of this, when children face a school environment at the

elementary level and surrounded by negative behavior by some teachers and students alike, their self-esteem become more negative and pessimistic.

Adolescence

Adolescence stage play a prominent and vital role in formation of personal future, whereas at this stage adolescence begins to observe the changes that occur to him/her and they start to accurate observation about changing in many aspect of human life such as surrounding environment, either external or internal environment. Also, during this stage, adolescents develop cognitively and this type of development affects the other level of knowledge such as sexual, social and cultural knowledge. For instance, he/she notice the changes in their pudendum and external genitalia. Characterized of adolescence state of instability and perplexity, Adolescence hesitates between staying in its current state and heading towards the outside world. More precisely in current stage, adolescent confounded whether to become independent or dependent in his/her life. They face different types of environment and therefore they face difficult in integration and adaptation with various types of environments. Relying on how these adolescents coping with these adaptations and how they handle different problems which might face it in their life; they structure their personalities and identities. Normally, adolescent's self-esteem develop when they coping with life problems, because before this stage, they were children and they found full supporting from their family and teachers meanwhile, in this stage they found awkwardness and embarrassment to ask their parents or teachers about puberty, physical changing or their emotions. While, they can express and discuss their feeling and emotions with their friends and peers who are on similar level such as childhood friends without any embarrassment. Therefore, adolescent have ability to absorb the feedback of friends, which have an effect on their self-esteem (Branden, 2001).

Adulthood

With growth of human life his /her self-esteem concepts increase to reach its peak within the age of 60 years. Many psychologists believed, such as Ericsson that self-worth feelings of the individual as a result of the individual to take a high profile in the community or at work or other, which would enhance the emergence of feelings of self-esteem larger than before.(Richard W. Robinset al, 2002). Some related to the concept of self-esteem theories suggests that the mid-life period is characterized by the endeavor of human rights for supremacy and control of himself and his environment. Congruous with these theoretical

contemplations, as a result of the growing maturity in adulthood stage, the individual's personality begins to change; this shows clearly the most people in emotional stability and a high level of conscience.

The Elderly People

Many researchers found and for both male and female that self-esteem is comparatively elevated in childhood stage and will reduce through adolescence stage and later in adulthood stage will rise progressively again and finally tends to reduce again in old age stage (Orth & Robins, 2014).

The self-esteem does not remain the same as previously as we have referred above and theories of personal psychology suggest that changes occur to human since he was a child until senility. It is worthwhile that self-esteem does not show major and significant normative changes over time, but change will occur as a result of the response of transformations and events in the life of the individual (Trzesniewski et al, 2004). Such a shift in human developmental can adjust or readdress life trajectories by changing human behavior, mental process and the circumstances that form the setting for an event, statement, or idea. Because of conflicting demands in an individual's life his/her life innings will change and begin local changes to emerge causing reduction in self-esteem, influenced by emotional ties, individual relationships with his peers as well as affected and will lead to high level of instability in more than aspect of his/her life such as losing or impairment of social life and /or problems with physical functioning (Ex, impairment of memory, decay in health, slow and weak body movement) which leads to be isolated from whole society and stay away from his/her friends and relatives (Baltes & Mayer, 1999). According to study of Jaquish and Ripple (1981), they found that adults decline their self-esteem (low self-esteem) after they exceed age 60 years old comparing with high self-esteem between 40 to less than 60 years old. Psychological studies and research has shown that a person (either male or female) with the progress his age, his/her self-esteem will declining and this was confirmed by the results of Tiggemann and Lynch (2001) study and Ranzijn et al (1998) study where the results of these studies showed that old people (more than 70 years old) had slightly lower self-esteem than young people.

Significance of Study

The concept of self-esteem has an important impact on the growth of individual ability and in different areas of his/her life and it will not be done only through the understanding of the role of the human self-esteem and how to enhance its capabilities, individual and social, in order to reach the best performance. The main point of current study is to investigate the self-esteem with A'Sharqiyah University (ASU)

students, precisely, psychology students in A'Sharqiyah University (ASU) in Sultanate of Oman. The essential objective of current research is to identify the extent of the impact of the performance of psychology students at A'Sharqiyah University (ASU) in Oman with level of self-esteem. There is another reason for this research is to recognize the gender dissimilarity of self-esteem between psychology students in A'Sharqiyah University (ASU) in Oman.

Participants

Total students populations in current research is about (N=93) psychology students which they are studying in Business and Economy department in A'Sharqiyah University in Oman. Aged students ranged from 20 to 30. Researcher divided them between male and female, where the total number of students reached (84) female students which they accounted (93%) and only (09) are male students which are constitute (7%) from total number of whole students. The reasons for such a large difference between male and female students are related to whole student's society in A'Sharqiyah University, where the number of female students is estimated about 95% of the total students. Students selected through random sampling method and based on the degree of their accessibility to participation in current research.

Instruments

Researcher located the participations (students) standard of self-esteem through Rosenberg scale which consists of 10 paragraphs/items. Rosenberg scale of self-esteem consists of 10 vertebrae and classified for four-point Likert scale, ranging as follows: strongly disagree, disagree, agree and strongly disagree. Researcher add one point which neutral because of privacy of students in A'Sharqiyah University. The paragraphs of Rosenberg scale distributed randomly between positives and negatives. So, items 1,3,4,7 and 10 considered as positive accent items while items 2,5,6,8 and 10 considered negative accent. The result is calculated according to this scale as follows: 0 to 30, where (30) degree is the highest score of self-esteem while the (0) degree is the lowest score of the self-esteem. And regarding for Rosenberg self-esteem scale reliability, it reached to 0.832 (Martin et al, 2007). The reliability of this study showed 0.626 which is also acceptable Table (1). This is due to the privacy of the community, whereas Omani society has different types than other societies.

TABLE 1. Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.626	10

According to table (2), results showed that the highest mean was for first year students (M=3.9091) followed by fourth year students (M=3.7860) then second year students (M=3.7286) and finally third year students (M=3.6708).

TABLE 2. Mean and Standard Deviation Descriptive

No.	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
1	11	3.9091	.64102
2	7	3.7286	.67259
3	24	3.6708	.46013
4	51	3.8216	.47045
Total	93	3.7860	.50359

And to verify the significance of differences in academic year, researcher used one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) and table (3) shows the summary of it, which shows the variable of academic year was not statistically significant.

TABLE 3. Summary of one-way analysis of variance ANOVA

Source of variance	SS	df	MS	F	Sig.
Between Groups	.573	3	.191	.746	.527
Within Groups	22.759	89	.256		
Total	23.332	92			

While for age variable, researcher used Pearson's Correlation to measure the relationship between student age and self-esteem, where a result showed that high significant level and shows that students' Self-esteem of higher education increases whenever the student progresses in age. Table (4) shows a positive relationship between self-esteem and student progressing in age.

TABLE 4. Pearson Correlations

		Mean Total
Age	Pearson Correlation	.218
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.036
	N	93

Discussion

The primary objective in this study was to highlighting identifies the self-esteem among Psychology students in A'Sharqiyah University in Sultanate of Oman. Results of the current study showed that self-

esteem and for both male and female students in high education in A'Sharqiyah University in Oman affected by age factor. Where the results showed that the student at the university level increases his/her self-esteem as he/she progresses in age. The results of the current study are consistent with the study (Orth & Robins, 2014) and Tiggemann and Lynch (2001) whose results indicate that self-esteem are high at the young age of human life such as in 20th and 30th. The results of the study did not reach any correlation between self-esteem and the student's academic year in higher education in A'Sharqiyah University in Oman. The result shows that the student in higher education- in Oman- remains an estimate of his self-ranging position and do not affected by academics year.

The interpretation of this result which indicates of increasing in self-esteem with both genders, male and female, in high education in Omanis due to several reasons such as rise of maturation levels with young comparing with childhood stage. This is motivating higher education students to adapt to various life problems. This is what Eriksson found in (Richard W. Robinset al, 2002), those feelings of self-esteem increase as individual's age, especially after childhood stage until old age.

Finally, the current study results are consistent with the results of a study of Forzi & Not (2003) whose results are close to the results of the current study.

As for the study variable for the academic year, the results of current study for academic year variable found not statistically significant.

Conclusion

The life of human goes through stages, starting with childhood, followed by adolescence then adulthood, then adulthood and later elderly stage and then finally death. Each stage has its own characteristics. Often, some personal traits appear at some stage, including self-esteem, which usually appear and develop with the growth and progress of the human being. Results of the current study showed that self-esteem and for both male and female students in high education in A'Sharqiyah University in Oman affected by age factor. Where the results showed that the student at the university level increases his/her self-esteem as he/she progresses in age. This study found there is no significant differences in level of self-esteem between male and females, where both male and female students was characterized by clear rise in self-esteem. Also, this study found that level of self-esteem is adversely affected due to the transition from adolescences stage to adulthood stage. The results of the current study also found the academic year

variable is not statistically significant. Finally, the results of current study have significant effects for parent, educationalists and students where the considerate on self-esteem might develop their understanding, knowledge and scientific prospect about everything that goes on around them and also they can understand themselves and the society around them.

References

- American Psychological Association. *Developing Adolescents: A Reference for Professionals*, 750 First Street, NE Washington, DC (2002).
- Baltes, P. B., & Mayer, K. U. *The Berlin Aging Study: Aging from 70 to 100*. Cambridge, England: Cambridge University Press. (1999).
- Branden, Nathaniel. *The Psychology of Self-Esteem 32nd Edition: A revolutionary approach to self-understanding that launched a new era in Modern psychology*. San Francisco: Jossey-Bass. (2001).
- Cooper smith, S. *The Antecedents of Self-Esteem*. San Francisco: W. H. Freeman and Company. (1967).
- Crocker, J., & Wolfe, C. T. Contingencies of Self-Worth. *Psychological Review*, 108,593-623. Retrieved February 7, 2011 from JSTOR. (2001).
- Forzi, M., & Not, E. Correlatidell'autostima in relazioneadetàe sesso. [Factors of self-esteem as regards age and gender]. *Bollenttino di PsicologiaApplicata*, 241, 27-36. Retrieved February 16, 2011 from ScienceDirect. (2003).
- Jaquish, G. A., & Ripple, R. E. Cognitive creative abilities and self-esteem across the adult life-span. *Human Development*, 24, 110– 119. (1981).
- Katz, L. How Can We Strengthen Children's Self Esteem. ERIC Clearinghouse on Elementary and Early Childhood Education. Online at: http://www.kidsource.com/kidsource/content2/strengthen_children_self.html. (1996).
- Macmillan Dictionary for Students Macmillan, Pan Ltd. (1981), page 14, 456.
- Malbi, R. S., & Reasoner, R. W. *Self-Esteem, Enhancing*. Kuala Lumpur: Self-Esteem Seminars Sdn. Bhd. Retrieved February 3, 2011 from JSTOR. (2000).

© Dr. Esam Al-lawati

- Martin-Albo, J., Núñez, J. L., Navarro, J. G., & Grijalvo, F. The Rosenberg Self-Esteem Scale: Translation and Validation in University Students. *The Spanish Journal of Psychology*, 10(2), 458-467. (2007).
- Orth, U., & Robins, R. W. The development of self-esteem. *Current Directions in Psychological Science*, 23, 381–387. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1177/0963721414547414>. (2014).
- Ragda, Shareem. *The psychology of adolescence*. AlMasera House, Jordan. (2007).
- Ranzjin, R., Keeves, J., Luszcz, M., & Feather, N. T. The role of self-perceived usefulness and competence in the self-esteem of elderly adults: Confirmatory factor analyses of the Bachman revision of Rosenberg's Self-Esteem Scale. *Journals of Gerontology: Psychological Sciences and Social Sciences*, 53(B), 1998, 96–104.
- Richard W. Robins, Kali H. Trzesniewski, Jessica L. Tracy, Samuel D. Gosling, Jeff Potter. Global Self-Esteem across the Life Span. *Psychology and Aging*. Vol. 17, No. 3, 423–434. (2002).
- Tam, C. L., & Fatimah Yusooff. The Effects of Family Functioning on Self-Esteem of Children. *European Journal of Social Sciences*, 9(4), 2009, 643-650.
- Tiggemann, M., & Lynch, J. E. Body image across the life span in adult women: The role of self-objectification. *Developmental Psychology*, 2001, 243–253.
- Trzesniewski, K. H., Robins, R. W., Roberts, B. W., & Caspi, A. Personality and self-esteem development across the life span. In P. T. Costa & I. C. Siegler (Eds.), *Recent advances in psychology and aging* (pp. 163–185). Amsterdam, the Netherlands: Elsevier Science. (2004).